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An Empirical Analysis of Affecting Factors the Demand for Housing Finance

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Abstract

Own house is a dream of every people. Each people want to have at least shelter. It is a basic need of human beings for their survival. Most of the people are still deprived from shelter in this country. The Government of India has made its best effort to give a own house to all citizens of the country have a house of his/her own. The study has been conducted in Indore city of Madhya Pradesh. Primary aim of the study was to ascertain factors those affect demand for housing finance. And further it has been examined whether such variables like occupation, disposable income, EMI and interest rate, would play a part in ascertaining the demand for housing finance. The outcomes of the study reflect that all variables except occupation are important and are the drivers of demand for housing finance in the study area. On the basis of outcomes, government and bank should make advancement procedures of housing finance more elastic and simple. Housing finance on less rate of interest and tax rebate on housing should be promoted and enhanced.

1. Introduction

Starting with the basic human needs it is very important for a human to have food, clothing and shelter for their survival. In this section shelter need of human is being focussed. Shelter in other words can be said as house, home, etc. but to have a house people have to invest some amount of their hard earn money to build a house.

Major problem with this country is that people need their privacy, space, and security in their house i.e. they need economic and social security which leads to environmental degeneration. The constant strife for house ownership has lead to personal social disorganization.

It is been stated that real estate business or housing is the second major employer of the people in our country India after agriculture. India in the past decade has seen the growth in the real estate business because of the citizen of the country are investing their money in the housing sector whether it is for personal use or for rent or as an asset.

In order to fulfil these desires people have to take loan from the banks or from any other financial institutions. So there are several kinds of housing loan offered by the banks or the financial institutions which are given according to the requirement of the person. People in order to make their dream come true apply for house loans, this not only fulfils their wishes but also provide the tax benefit too.

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